

Physicochemical Investigation on some Ternary Complexes of Dioxouranium(VI)

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This paper reports potentiometric studies on some mixed ligand complexes of $U^{VI}O_2$, using nitrilotriacetic acid as primary ligand, and succinic, malic, maleic, fumaric, malonic, adipic, itaconic phthalic and mandelic acids as secondary ligands. The thermodynamic parameters, viz. ΔG , ΔH and ΔS have been evaluated. The ΔG and ΔH values have been further separated into their electrostatic components ΔG_e , ΔH_e and cratic components ΔG_c and ΔH_c . Effects of change in dielectric constant and change in ionic strength have been studied on a few systems. The results are correlated on the basis of steric and structural characteristics of the chelates formed.

RECENTLY, few reports have appeared on the ternary and quaternary complexes of $U^{VI}O_2$, using various simple and substituted carboxylic acids¹⁻⁴, phenols⁵ and hetero acids^{6,7} but no attempt appears to have been made on ternary complexes of $U^{VI}O_2$, using aminopolycarboxylic acids as primary ligand. The present study has been made to explore the possibility of expansion of coordination number of central uranium atom in $U^{VI}O_2$ (where two coordinating positions are already satisfied by two oxygen atoms) beyond six in solution. The primary ligand chosen is nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA) which acts as tetradentate, whereas all secondary ligands, viz. succinic (SUC), malic (MA), maleic (MAE), fumaric (FA), malonic (MLA), itaconic (ITCA), adipic (AA), phthalic (PTHA) and mandelic (MDA) acid act as bidentate ligands. Modified form of Irving-Rosotti's pH-titration technique⁸ has been employed to determine the stability constant, $\log K_{ML_2}^{M}$. All studies have been performed at constant ionic strength of 2 M (KNO_3) and at three different temperatures, viz. 5, 25 and 45°. The thermodynamic parameters, ΔG , ΔH , ΔS , ΔG_c , ΔH_c , ΔG_e and ΔH_e have been evaluated. Effects of change in dielectric constant and ionic strengths have been studied on $U^{VI}O_2$ -NTA-MAE and $U^{VI}O_2$ -NTA-PTHA systems. For studying the change in dielectric constants, the compositions used were 15, 30, 45, 60 and 75% (v/v) dioxane at $\mu=0.1$ M, and for the change in ionic strength, different ionic strengths used were 0.05, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3 and 0.4 M. These studies were carried out at 25°.

Experimental

Material: A stock solution of $UO_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (B.D.H.) was prepared by dissolving requisite

quantity of pure sample in nitric acid to prevent hydrolysis of the metal ions. The metal content was estimated gravimetrically⁹. 2 M KNO_3 was prepared by dissolving requisite quantity in double-distilled water, while 0.2 M HNO_3 was prepared by diluting nitric acid (A.R.) and estimated potentiometrically. 0.01 M NTA and 0.02 M secondary ligand solutions were prepared by dissolving requisite quantity in double-distilled water and estimated potentiometrically. Carbonate-free sodium hydroxide solution was prepared by standard method¹⁰. Dioxane was purified by standard method¹¹.

A ECIL expanded scale pH-meter fitted with glass-calomel assembly with an accuracy of ± 0.02 unit was used to measure $[H^+]$ of the solution. Agar-agar salt-bridge saturated with KNO_3 was used to prevent formation of chloro complexes. Temperature was maintained constant ($\pm 0.02^\circ$) with the help of a MK-70 automatic thermostatic ultracryostat. All the experiments were done in an inert atmosphere by bubbling nitrogen through the solution throughout the course of titration.

Procedure: Four mixtures were prepared as follows: (A) 2.0×10^{-3} M nitric acid, (B) 2.0×10^{-3} M nitric acid + 1.0×10^{-3} M secondary ligand solution, (C) 2.0×10^{-3} M nitric acid + 1.0×10^{-3} M uranyl nitrate + 1.0×10^{-3} M NTA solution and (D) 2.0×10^{-3} M nitric acid + 1.0×10^{-3} M uranyl nitrate + 1.0×10^{-3} M NTA + 1.0×10^{-3} M secondary ligand solution. These four mixtures were prepared in such a manner that the concentration of common ingredients were identical in each case. The ionic strength was maintained constant at 0.2 M by adding an appropriate amount of KNO_3 solution. The total volume of all the systems was maintained constant by adding double-distilled water. The

ratio of M : A : L was maintained 1 : 1 : 1. While studying the effect of change in dielectric constant, required volume of dioxane was added and for variation in ionic strength an appropriate quantity of KNO_3 was added. A graph between pH meter reading and volume of alkali added was plotted. The four curves so obtained were named as (A) acid curve, (B) secondary ligand curve, (C) primary complexation curve and (D) mixed ligand complexation curve.

Results

Proton-ligand stability constants of secondary ligands: The values of $\bar{n}_A$ at various pH values have been calculated from curves A and B. The proton-ligand stability constants have been evaluated by (A) interpolation at half $\bar{n}_A$ value and (B) interpolation at various $\bar{n}_A$ values. The values of proton-ligand stability constants at different temperatures in aqueous medium have been presented in Table 1. Tables 2 and 3 have values of proton-ligand stability constant calculated by method (B) at different dielectric constants and at different

ionic strengths, respectively at 25°. The error limit for $\log K_1^H$ is ± 0.04 and that for $\log K_2^H$ is ± 0.06 . These values have been taken into account while calculating the formation constants.

Metal-ligand stability constants: The mixed ligand formation constant, $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$, have been evaluated from horizontal difference, $(V_4 - V_3) - (V_2 - V_1)$, where V_1 , V_2 , V_3 and V_4 are volumes of NaOH required to reach the same pH on curves A, B, C and D, respectively. The formation constants have been evaluated by two methods (A) interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ value and (B) interpolation at various $\bar{n}$ values. The formation constant obtained at different temperatures and at constant ionic strength of 0.2 M in aqueous medium are presented in Table 1. While calculating formation constants at different dielectric constants appropriate correction factors are applied¹². The values of $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ at different dielectric constants and at different ionic strengths calculated by method (B) have been given in Tables 2 and 3, respectively. The error limits for $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ is ± 0.08 .

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM

$\mu = 0.2 M \text{KNO}_3$		Temp., °C					
System	Constant	5		25		45	
		A	B	A	B	A	B
SUC	$\log K_1^H$	5.20	5.23	5.16	5.16	5.12	5.14
	$\log K_2^H$	3.97	4.01	3.88	3.86	3.80	3.80
MA	$\log K_1^H$	4.88	4.88	4.80	4.80	4.70	4.70
	$\log K_2^H$	2.48	2.48	2.40	2.38	2.28	2.25
MAE	$\log K_1^H$	5.84	5.83	5.78	5.80	5.74	5.77
	$\log K_2^H$	3.06	2.99	3.00	2.97	2.95	2.95
FA	$\log K_1^H$	4.26	4.26	4.21	4.18	4.16	4.15
	$\log K_2^H$	3.10	3.10	3.03	3.02	2.98	3.00
MLA	$\log K_1^H$	5.35	5.36	5.23	5.25	5.10	5.12
	$\log K_2^H$	2.70	2.70	2.68	2.68	2.65	2.66
AA	$\log K_1^H$	5.65	5.62	5.50	5.48	5.40	5.44
	$\log K_2^H$	4.10	4.10	4.05	4.06	4.02	4.02
ITCA	$\log K_1^H$	5.64	5.62	5.52	5.48	5.40	5.40
	$\log K_2^H$	3.54	3.52	3.51	3.48	3.40	3.45
PTHA	$\log K_1^H$	4.79	4.77	4.71	4.73	4.60	4.62
	$\log K_2^H$	2.55	2.56	2.51	2.54	2.48	2.50
MDA	$\log K_1^H$	3.49	3.48	3.40	3.38	3.31	3.34
UV^2O_8 -NTA-SUC	$\log K_{MAL}^{NTA}$	3.90	3.88	3.85	3.83	3.78	3.77
UV^2O_8 -NTA-MA	$\log K_{MAL}^{NTA}$	4.64	4.62	4.40	4.38	4.12	4.09
UV^2O_8 -NTA-MAE	$\log K_{MAL}^{NTA}$	5.20	5.18	5.06	5.07	4.86	4.86
UV^2O_8 -NTA-FA	$\log K_{MAL}^{NTA}$	4.25	4.23	4.04	4.01	3.84	3.82
UV^2O_8 -NTA-MLA	$\log K_{MAL}^{NTA}$	4.80	4.80	4.62	4.64	4.44	4.43
UV^2O_8 -NTA-AA	$\log K_{MAL}^{NTA}$	4.24	4.22	4.12	4.11	4.06	4.02
UV^2O_8 -NTA-ITCA	$\log K_{MAL}^{NTA}$	4.62	4.61	4.42	4.45	4.32	4.30
UV^2O_8 -NTA-PTHA	$\log K_{MAL}^{NTA}$	4.04	4.04	3.94	3.93	3.83	3.81
UV^2O_8 -NTA-MDA	$\log K_{MAL}^{NTA}$	3.60	3.60	3.54	3.52	3.50	3.45

TABLE 2—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS IN DIFFERENT COMPOSITION OF DIOXANE-WATER MIXTURES

$\mu = 0.1 M$, Temp. = 25°

System	Constant	Dioxane %					
		0	15	30	45	60	75
MAE	$\log K_{11}^H$	5.84	5.89	5.96	6.08	6.28	6.50
	$\log K_{22}^H$	3.06	3.13	3.17	3.28	3.40	3.64
PTHA	$\log K_{11}^H$	4.82	4.86	4.94	5.04	5.24	5.48
	$\log K_{22}^H$	2.60	2.63	2.72	2.88	3.12	3.36
$U^{VI}O_2$ -NTA-MAE	$\log K_{MAL}^{NTA}$	5.22	5.28	5.40	5.58	5.81	6.08
$U^{VI}O_2$ -NTA-PTHA	$\log K_{MAL}^{NTA}$	4.06	4.12	4.20	4.42	4.64	4.90

TABLE 3—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS IN DIFFERENT MEDIUM OF IONIC STRENGTHS
Temp. = 25°

System	Constant	Ionic strength, <i>M</i>				
		0.05	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4
MAE	$\log K_{11}^H$	5.91	5.84	5.78	5.64	5.52
	$\log K_{22}^H$	3.16	3.06	2.97	2.84	2.73
PTHA	$\log K_{11}^H$	4.92	4.82	4.71	4.62	4.48
	$\log K_{22}^H$	2.68	2.60	2.51	2.40	2.32
$U^{VI}O_2$ -NTA-MAE	$\log K_{MAL}^{NTA}$	5.35	5.22	5.06	4.94	4.82
$U^{VI}O_2$ -NTA-PTHA	$\log K_{MAL}^{NTA}$	4.18	4.06	3.93	3.81	3.71

$U^{VI}O_2$ -NTA primary complex formation starts at an early pH ~ 2.0 and is completed at pH ~ 3.0. The primary complex is stable upto pH ~ 5.6 after which the curve shows diversion indicating hydrolysis. In all the ternary systems the difference, $(V_4 - V_3) - (V_2 - V_1)$ is negligible upto pH ~ 3.2 after which the mixed ligand complex formation starts. In each case the $\bar{n}$ value reaches upto ~ 0.8. Since the primary complex, $U^{VI}O_2$ -NTA is very stable and is formed at lower pH, there is no possibility of replacement reaction.

Thermodynamic parameters: The values of the change in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) have been evaluated at constant ionic strength of 0.2 M KNO_3 , with the help of temperature coefficient and Gibbs-Helmholtz equation¹². The error limits for ΔG , ΔH and ΔS values are ± 0.10 kcal mol⁻¹, ± 0.5 kcal mol⁻¹ and ± 2 cal K⁻¹ mol⁻¹, respectively. The ΔG and ΔH values

have been further separated into the cratic components ΔG_c and ΔH_c and electrostatic components ΔG_e and ΔH_e to know the extent of participation of covalent and ionic bonding¹⁴. The values of these thermodynamic parameters have been presented in Table 4.

Discussion

The present work was aimed to explore the possibility of expansion of coordination number of central uranium atom of $U^{VI}O_2$ to greater than six. The primary ligand, NTA is tetradentate and hence formation of $U^{VI}O_2$ -NTA complex will make coordination number of the central uranium atom to six (two positions being occupied by two oxygen atoms). Hence, the formation of mixed ligand complex will need the expansion of coordination number from six to eight. The formation of mixed ligand complex is evident from (i) horizontal

TABLE 4—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF $U^{VI}O_2$ -NTA-L SYSTEM

System	$-\Delta G$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta H$ kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔS kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta G_e$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta H_e$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta G_c$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta H_c$ kcal mol ⁻¹
$U^{VI}O_2$ -NTA-SUC	5.22	1.1	14.0	4.77	1.71	2.83	-0.6
$U^{VI}O_2$ -NTA-MA	5.97	5.3	2.0	2.26	0.81	6.09	4.5
$U^{VI}O_2$ -NTA-MAE	6.91	4.3	9.0	3.63	1.3	5.66	3.0
$U^{VI}O_2$ -NTA-FA	5.46	3.9	5.0	2.86	1.0	4.99	2.9
$U^{VI}O_2$ -NTA-MLA	6.32	4.6	6.0	3.04	1.1	5.67	3.5
$U^{VI}O_2$ -NTA-AA	5.71	1.9	13.0	4.55	1.6	3.55	0.3
$U^{VI}O_2$ -NTA-ITCA	6.00	3.1	10.0	3.89	1.4	4.5	1.7
$U^{VI}O_2$ -NTA-PTHA	5.36	2.3	10.0	4.01	1.4	3.73	0.8
$U^{VI}O_2$ -NTA-MDA	4.80	1.5	11.0	4.16	1.5	3.03	0.02

distance, $(V_4 - V_3) - (V_2 - V_1)$ which increases till $\bar{n} \sim 0.8$ where the values of pL systematically decrease and (ii) increase in pH of the precipitation of mixed ligand complex to ~ 6.6 from $pH \sim 6.0$ of precipitation of primary complex, which indicates the suppression of hydrolysis due to mixed ligand complex formation. The stepwise formation of mixed ligand complex is evident from the fact that the horizontal difference, $(V_4 - V_3) - (V_2 - V_1)$, is negligible upto $pH \sim 3.0$. This is the expected trend since the stability of binary complex with NTA is more than the binary complex with the secondary ligand. The formation of mixed ligand complex is favoured as seen from the positive values of entropy in all the cases. The negative values of ΔH indicate exothermic nature of the reaction while negative values of ΔG indicate spontaneity of the reaction. In case of SUC, AA, MDA and PTHA complexes, the ΔH values are low but the reactions are supported by equally high ΔS values. In most of the cases the values of cratic components are more negative than electrostatic components, indicating participation of covalent bonding in the complexes formed.

In all the systems primary ligand being the same, the changing factor which governs order of stability is the secondary ligand. The order of stability is governed by (i) basicity of the ligand, (ii) size of the chelate ring formed and (iii) chelating characteristic of the ligand. The order of basicity amongst the aliphatic carboxylic acids (considering release of both the protons during complexation) is $AA > SUC \approx ITCA > MAE > MLA > FA \approx MA$. Among these ligands MLA forms six-membered ring while AA forms nine-membered ring. The observed order of stability of these mixed ligand chelates is $MAE > MLA > MA \approx ITCA > AA \approx FA > SUC$. This order can be justified as follows. (i) The higher stability of MAE complex may be due to the presence of conjugate double bond in the ligand which increases stability of the complex due to exocyclic conjugation. (ii) The ligand MA has electron withdrawing OH group which decreases basicity of the ligand and hence, the stability of the mixed ligand complex formed is higher than expected. (iii) MLA forms stable six-membered ring and hence, gives higher stability to $U^{VI}O_2$ -NTA-MLA ternary complex. (iv) ITCA has methylene group which lowers the stability of

the complex. (v) AA forms big nine-membered ring and hence, this chelate has lower stability.

Among PTHA and MDA, the complex with the former ligand is more stable, obviously because of its higher basicity. However, MDA complex has higher stability than expected which might be due to small chelate ring and presence of electron withdrawing OH group in the ligand.

Table 2 shows the values of proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants in different concentrations of dioxane-water mixtures. The results show that the values of stability constants increase with the increase in percentage of dioxane. The plots of $\log K_1$ vs mole fraction of dioxane are linear over the entire range indicating that ion-ion interactions involving the metal ion and the anionic oxygen donors of the ligand increase to a greater extent than the ion-dipole interaction between the metal and the solvent molecule as the dipole moment of the medium decreases.

An observation of Table 3 which has values of proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants with change in ionic strength, indicates that the values of stability constants decrease with the increase in ionic strength.

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